

A Study on Sodium Borohydride Assisted Dithionite Bleaching of Mixed Office Wastes

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Abstract – In this study, the effects of sodium borohydride (NaBH₄) addition on the mechanical and optical properties of papers in dithionite bleaching processes, which are widely used in MOW bleaching, were investigated. In the bleaching processes, the dithionite charge was kept constant at 0.4%, while the NaBH₄ charge was applied at four different rates of 0.0%, 0.5%, 1.0% and 1.5%. To increase the bleaching effect of dithionite, EDTA was also used in half the dithionite dosage. After the bleaching processes, the pulps were washed with tap water to remove chemicals. Test papers with 80 grammages (g/m²) were produced to determine the mechanical and optical properties of bleached pulps. It was observed that the mechanical and optical properties were improved by adding NaBH₄ to the bleaching solutions. When 1.5% NaBH₄ was added to the bleaching solution, the brightness increased by 4.9% and the breaking length by 8.3%. According to these findings, greater optical and mechanical properties may be obtained by adding NaBH₄ to the bleaching solution in conventional dithionite bleaching methods, as well as by lowering the quantity of dithionite charge.

Keywords – Mixed Office Waste, Dithionite, Sodium Borohydride, Bleaching, Pulp

I. INTRODUCTION

Raw materials for the paper and board production are mainly obtained from trees (wood), annual plants and waste papers (El-Sayed et al., 2020; Haile et al., 2021; Tutuş et al., 2022). Waste paper recycling is both ecologically harmless and more cost-effective than pulping it from wood and annual plants (Him et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2013). One of the most suitable waste paper recycling methods is to produce paper of the same grade from waste paper (Çiçekler & Tutuş, 2021). Pulp has to be bleached several times during the manufacturing process of white paper. Because they contain chlorine, the chemicals used in bleaching sequences are less toxic to the environment.

Using mixed office waste (MOW) in the manufacture of white paper would be less polluting and more cost effective. However, in 2018 only a third of office paper was made from wood-free raw

materials. The basic limitation of using MOW as fiber to produce high-quality recycled paper is that it contains a significant proportion of difficult-to-deink non-impact (laser and xerographic) sheets, ranging from 50% to 80% (Çiçekler & Tutuş, 2021; Olson et al., 1993; Tsatsis et al., 2017).

Many types of waste paper are deinked in order to remove ink prior to the making of fresh paper. Depending on the type of paper entering the system and the needs of the end product, a number of deinking processes can be used. The most popular deinking techniques are flotation, washing, and bleaching (Hietala et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 2020; Saxena & Singh Chauhan, 2017).

By using bleaching chemicals such as sodium dithionite and hydrogen peroxide, the dyes in the inks are removed and the brightness value of the pulp is increased throughout the pulp bleaching process. This process is applied to recycled pulp during or after pulping and is used to produce

tissue, office paper and newsprint with appropriate brightness levels (Knutson & Ragauskas, 2004; Xu et al., 2015).

When color correction by removal of dyes is required in addition to fiber brightness, dithionite bleaching is an essential mechanism in the deinking process. The active ingredient in the dithionite (hydrosulfite) bleaching process is sodium dithionite, a light yellow crystalline solid (Krishnan et al., 2020). The main function of sodium dithionite is to act on the dye component of the pulp (Isoaho et al., 2019).

Borohydride is a typical boron compound used in pulp manufacture. It is commonly used to increase pulp yield by adding it to boiling liquor in specified amounts, and it is also used in pulp bleaching for its bleaching properties (Çiçekler et al., 2022; Çiçekler et al., 2021). In multi-stage bleaching operations, sodium borohydride (NaBH_4) is increasingly being used as a reducing agent. It converts carbonyl groups to alcohol groups more effectively than sodium or zinc hydrosulfite and improves reflectivity across a wider range (Lehto et al., 2021; Zaccaron et al., 2022).

The effects of sodium borohydride addition in dithionite bleaching of mixed office waste on bleaching yield as well as optical and mechanical properties of pulps were investigated in this study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The pulp used in the study was obtained by recycling and deinking mixed office wastes according to INGEDE standards. Whiteness, brightness, tensile and burst indices of the pulps were 68.57 ISO%, 84.54 ISO%, 22.1 Nm/g and 2.15 kPa.m²/g respectively. All chemicals used in pulping, deinking and bleaching processes were purchased from Merck (Germany).

The recycled pulps of mixed office wastes were bleached with sodium dithionite under four different parameters, as shown in Table 1. The charge of NaBH_4 was adjusted during the bleaching process while the charge of sodium dithionite ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4$), consistency, duration, and temperature remained constant.

After preparing the bleaching liquors described in Table 1, the pulps were put in polyethylene bags, then placed in a water bath with a thermostat to control the temperature. After bleaching, the

pulps were washed with hot and cold water to eliminate any chemicals.

Table 1. Conditions of mixed office waste pulp bleaching

Conditions	Unit	Value
$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4$ charge	%	0.4
EDTA charge	%	0.2
NaBH_4 charge	%	0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5
Temperature	°C	75
Time	Min	60
Consistency	%	5

The bleached pulps were beaten with a Hollander beater to a freeness level of 40 ± 3 SR° (Schopper Riegler). Then, 10 sheets with grammages of 70 g/m² per tested sequence were formed using an ISO 5269/2 sheet forming (Rapid-Kothen). The papers were also tested for whiteness (ISO 2470), brightness (ISO 11475), tensile index (ISO 1924-2) and burst index (ISO 2759). Frank Tensile Tester was used to determine the tensile strength of the papers. The burst strength of the paper was determined using Mullen Tester. Whiteness and brightness values of the papers measured with the Datacolor Elrepho 450x spectrometer.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the bleaching yields determined following dithionite bleaching process. In all bleaching operations, as previously stated, employed 0.4% sodium dithionite.

Table 2. Bleaching yields of MOW pulps

Conditions	NaBH_4 charge (%)	Yield (%)
UP	-	-
1	-	90.35
2	0.5	91.73
3	1.0	93.01
4	1.5	93.86

*UP refers to unbleached pulps

While the bleaching yield was determined to be 90.4% for dithionite bleaching without the use of NaBH_4 , this value rose by 1.38 units to 91.7% when 0.5% NaBH_4 was used. By converting the carbonyl group on the reducing ends of the cellulose chain to the hydroxyl group, NaBH_4 minimizes peeling during cooking/bleaching. Both cellulose and hemicellulose exhibit this reaction. As a result, the reaction minimizes yield losses

while increasing the yield of the resulting pulp (Çiçekler et al., 2022; Gümüşkaya et al., 2011; Zhibin et al., 2005). With the use of 1.5% NaBH₄, the bleaching yield increased by about 3.9% in MOW dithionite bleaching.

Figure 1. Tensile and burst indices of bleached MOW pulps with NaBH₄

Although lignin is brightened or removed by the chemicals used in pulp bleaching, they also have an impact on carbohydrates like cellulose and hemicellulose (Kang et al., 1995; Pouyet et al., 2014). The mechanical properties of the pulps were adversely affected by bleaching with sodium dithionite. As a result of dithionite bleaching of the pulps, the tensile index decreased by 17.2% while the burst index decreased by 11.2%. These decreases are due to the degradation of the fibers by the chemicals used in the bleaching processes. It can be clearly seen in Fig. 1 that the use of NaBH₄ eliminates the reductions in mechanical properties caused by bleaching processes. With the addition of 1.5% NaBH₄ to the bleach liquor, the tensile and burst indices increased by 20.1% and 8.4%, respectively.

The optical properties of the bleached pulps were indicated in Fig.2.

The whiteness and brightness values of the pulps obtained as a result of dithionite bleaching process without NaBH₄ were measured as 74.53 ISO% and 92.73 ISO%, respectively. During the dithionite bleaching process, the ink dyes were eliminated and the whiteness and brightness values of the pulps increased about 8.7% and 9.7%, respectively.

Figure 2. Whiteness and brightness values of bleached MOW pulps with NaBH₄

Because of their bleaching ability, boron compounds have a favorable effect on the brightness values. Studies have shown that boron compounds have an impact on brightness (Çiçekler et al., 2021; Istek & Gonteki, 2009; Lehto et al., 2021). In Fig. 2, increases in optical properties are observed in parallel with increases in the NaBH₄ charge added to the bleaching liquor. When bleaching MOW with dithionite, the addition of 1.5% NaBH₄ to the bleaching liquor increased the whiteness values from 74.53 ISO% to 80.9 ISO%, while the brightness values increased from 92.73 ISO to 97.3% ISO.

IV. CONCLUSION

The effects of adding NaBH₄ to the bleaching liquor on the bleaching yield, mechanical and optical properties of mixed office waste with dithionite were determined. The main conclusions that can be drawn are:

- The use of NaBH₄ increased bleaching yield by preventing the degradation of carbohydrates such as cellulose and hemicellulose during dithionite bleaching.
- The decreases in tensile and burst strengths after dithionite bleaching were eliminated by using NaBH₄.
- When the NaBH₄-free dithionite bleaching was compared to the dithionite bleaching using NaBH₄, it was found that the use of NaBH₄ improved the optical properties more.

As a result, it will be possible to produce pulps with high optical, mechanical and bleaching yield levels by using NaBH₄ in the dithionite bleaching process, and it will be possible to obtain this while using less dithionite charge by adding NaBH₄.

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